

Table 2. Effect of exogenous GA₃ on elongation of internodes and leaf sheath and expansion of leaf blade in rice varieties.

Variety/ treatment	Length of internode from top (cm)					Length of leaf sheath from top (cm)					Area of individual leaf from top (cm ²)				
	I	II	III	IV	V	I	II	III	IV	V	I	II	III	IV	V
<i>Dwarf mutant</i>															
Control	26	12	3	1	1	16	11	9	8	9	27	27	26	27	18
GA ₃	33	11	16	29	15	35	35	26	15	24	46	45	36	42	39
% of control	127	91	533	2900	1500	218	318	288	187	267	170	167	138	155	206
<i>Cigar</i>															
Control	16	10	3	1	1	20	12	12	11	9	48	47	33	22	15
GA ₃	18	13	6	3	2	23	14	10	14	10	55	55	41	19	-
% of control	112	130	200	200	200	115	117	83	127	111	114	117	124	86	-
<i>Nadula dwarf</i>															
Control	25	11	12	7	3	23	16	18	18	19	79	100	104	91	81
GA ₃	22	8	15	6	9	23	14	16	22	23	80	88	108	89	66
% of control	88	72	125	86	300	100	87	88	122	121	101	88	104	97	82
<i>Dee-geo-woo-gen</i>															
Control	31	14	16	8	6	36	26	27	23	26	56	80	79	67	46
GA ₃	30	16	18	30	10	35	34	26	24	24	49	76	66	57	56
% of control	96	114	112	275	150	97	130	96	104	92	87	95	83	85	121
<i>C14-8</i>															
Control	39	34	25	20	14	42	32	31	34	39	69	90	104	110	89
GA ₃	42	35	28	28	18	40	34	31	29	42	72	101	106	114	98
% of control	107	103	112	140	128	95	106	100	85	107	104	112	101	104	110

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of low light stress on photosynthesis, dry matter production, and grain yield in rice hybrids bred from two different cytoplasmic male sterile sources

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We compared the tolerance for low light of selected F₁ rice hybrids bred from two cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, IR62829A and IR58025A, during wet season in 1992 (see table). They were grown in 3-m² field plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing and fertilized with 60 kg N ha⁻¹. Wooden screens were used to create low light (50% of normal sun-light) from 35 d after transplanting until harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 340 cal cm⁻² d⁻¹). The split-plot design with three replications was used with the two light treatments in the main plots and the hybrids in the subplots. The photosynthetic rate (Pn) of the

Effect of shading on photosynthesis and yield in hybrids and restorers. Cuttack, India.^a

Hybrid/restorer	Pn (mg CO ₂ dm ⁻² h ⁻¹)		TDM (g m ⁻²)		Yield (g m ⁻²)		HI (%)	
	L	S	L	S	L	S	L	S
<i>Hybrids</i>								
IR62829 A/Swarna	41.6	29.1	1043	666	365	232	35	35
IR62829 A/Vajram	51.8	29.3	1377	818	665	269	48	33
IR58025 A/Swarna	51.6	29.2	952	582	356	167	38	35
IR58025 A/Vajram	37.4	25.4	947	695	352	176	37	26
<i>Restorers</i>								
Swarna	31.2	18.8	968	455	432	170	45	37
Vajram	48.5	30.7	1326	746	522	228	39	31
<i>Standard</i>								
Swarnaprabha	45.9	35.2	1141	703	520	218	46	31
Mean	44.0	28.2	1108	666	459	209	41	33
CD (5%)								
Variety (V)	0.71		54		22		3.4	
Treatment (T)	4.36		54		24		2.3	
V at same T	6.16		95		34		5.2	
T at same V	5.77		76		45		4.8	
<i>Heterosis (%) over restorer</i>								
IR62829 A/Swarna	33	55	8	46	-16	36	-22	-8
IR62829 A/Vajram	7	-5	4	10	27	18	26	6
IR58025 A/Swarna	51	55	-2	28	-18	-2	-15	-8
IR58025 A/Vajram	-23	-17	-29	-7	-33	-23	-5	-16
Mean	17	22	-5	19	-10	7	-4	-7

^aPn = photosynthetic rate, TDM = total dry matter, HI = harvest index, L = light, S = shaded.

second leaf at vegetative stage (40 d after planting) and the flag leaf at flowering was measured using a portable LI-6000 at near saturated light (above 1000 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). The hybrid IR62829A / Vajram showed highest Pn values but marginal (positive) and negative heterosis over restorers in light and shade, respectively. Swarna registered higher heterosis (over restorer) in Pn under both light and shade. The combining ability for Pn seems to be better with IR62829A for Vajram and IR58025A for Swarna.

Total dry matter (TDM) and grain yield were highest in the F₁ hybrids of IR62829A and the restorer Vajram. Harvest index was high in IR62829A / Vajram (only in light), whereas Swarna had higher values. The hybrid IR52829A/Vajram showed higher dry matter, yield, and harvest index than the standard check Swarnaprabha.

High positive heterosis for TDM and yield was found in the hybrids of the IR62829A CMS line under shade, whereas under light marginal heterosis was observed for TDM only. The

hybrids of IR58025A CMS line showed negative heterosis for yield and harvest index under both light and shade regimes (except IR58025A/Swarna for TDM under shade). The hybrid IR62829A / Swarna showed high heterosis for TDM and yield under shade; under normal light IR62829A/Vajram recorded higher values for yield and harvest index, but this hybrid showed higher grain yield under both conditions, indicating its agronomic superiority in yield with greater harvest index. ■

Estimation of elongation efficiency in deepwater rice varieties

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When submerged, deepwater rice shows rapid elongation of internode, leaf sheath, and leaf blade, the amount depending on variety. We studied 15 deepwater varieties for their relative elongation efficiency during the 1996 wet season at Cuttack. Three pots with two 37-d-old plants of each variety were submerged in a 110-cm deepwater tank. On the first day, water level was maintained at 40 cm, and on the following day it was raised to 110 cm. The height of plants was recorded before submergence and every 2 d during submergence, up to 10 d. The relative elongation efficiency indices of the varieties were calculated by the formula suggested by Singh (1982):

$$\text{Elongation efficiency index} = \frac{X(N-0) + X(N-2) + X(N-4) + X(N-6) + X(N-8)}{N(\text{Maximum elongation observed})}$$

where X₁, X₂, X₃, X₄, and X₅ stand for actual elongation (in cm) during first, second, third, fourth, and fifth observation, respectively, N is the total span in days (10) from submergence to last observation.

Actual elongation of 15 varieties after submergence for 10 d.

Variety	Actual elongation (cm 48 h ⁻¹)					Total (cm)	Elongation efficiency index
	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅		
Jalamagna	25.8	13.8	11.6	10.8	9.4	71.4	0.70
TCA4	21.8	15.5	12.0	8.5	8.5	66.3	0.65
Jalanidhi	10.2	7.6	22.6	11.1	15.5	67.0	0.52
NDGR410	17.8	20.6	21.1	5.2	2.8	67.5	0.69
Kariawa	16.8	13.4	9.0	16.3	15.3	70.8	0.59
LPR56-49	6.2	6.2	11.8	4.0	7.3	35.5	0.30
TCA282	13.4	13.4	17.0	4.7	5.6	54.1	0.52
TCA269	12.0	8.6	22.6	8.0	7.0	58.2	0.52
Madhukar	9.0	9.8	12.2	8.0	7.1	46.1	0.40
NDGR413	13.0	16.4	13.6	11.0	9.8	63.8	0.57
TCA12	12.6	12.0	16.4	8.5	7.1	56.6	0.52
Chakia 59	8.4	9.4	22.2	4.3	2.6	46.9	0.44
Jalapriya	8.8	6.0	13.6	7.2	5.6	41.2	0.36
Bojaz	12.2	8.4	21.6	2.8	2.3	47.3	0.47
LPR85	4.70	5.1	24.4	5.5	4.5	44.2	0.37

Jalamagna had the highest elongation efficiency index (0.70), followed by NDGR410 (0.69), TCA4 (0.65), and Kariawa (0.59) (see table). The higher indices of the above varieties might be attributed to attainment of maximum rate of elongation at an early stage (higher X₁ values), except for NDGR410, which had consistently high elongation rates up to the third observation (high X₁, X₂, and X₃ values). Most of the varieties attained maximum elongation rate after 6 d of submergence (higher X₃ values) and had comparatively low elongation efficiency indices. The varieties with elongation efficiency indices higher than 0.44 managed to penetrate the water surface while those below 0.44 remained submerged. ■

Histological variation among aromatic rice

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Fifteen popular aromatic genotypes were studied to ascertain the variation for histological traits in leaves and shoots. Photomicrographs of the transverse sections of leaves revealed that the cuticle in all genotypes was thin compared with that of the nonaromatic check, Mahsuri. The size